

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Lanthanon-tris(chlorosulphate) Complexes with Nitrogen and Oxygen Donors

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Manuscript received 15 March 1991, accepted 19 March 1992

Some eight coordinated complexes of Eu^{III}, Tm^{III} and Yb^{III} chlorosulphates with pyridine, pyridine-*N*-oxide, acridine and bipyridine have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, conductance magnetic and infrared spectral data. Spectroscopic investigation has shown that SO₂Cl⁻ groups and bipyridyl ligand are all coordinated to the metal ion in a bidentate manner whereas the other ligand groups are coordinated monodentately.

The interest in the chemistry of compounds containing coordinated SO₂Cl⁻ anion has increased rapidly in recent years¹. In continuation of our work on the synthesis and characterisation of the lanthanon complexes, we report here the preparation and characterisation of few complexes of Eu, Tm and Yb tris-chlorosulphates with pyridine (bipy), pyridine-*N*-oxide (pyNO), acridine (acr) and bipyridine (bipy) with a view to examining their stereochemistry and mode of coordination.

Results and Discussion

The result of chemical analysis (Table I) are in agreement with the proposed formulation of the complexes as Ln(SO₂Cl)₃L₃ (where L=pyridine, pyridine-*N*-oxide and acridine) and Ln(SO₂Cl)₃L (where L=2,2'-bipyridine).

The infrared spectra of the complexes display bands characteristic of the covalently bonded chlorosulphate groups. The spectra indicate an increase in the $\nu_1(A)$ vibration ($\sim 50\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which may be due to appreciable cation-anion interactions and symmetry lowering. The two-fold ν_2 and ν_4 modes split into two bands at 650 ± 10 , 685 ± 10 and 1250 ± 10 , $1180 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. These observations are suggestive of substantial covalent bonding between the metal ions and the SO₂Cl⁻ groups which is expected in view of $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding between sulphur and chlorine after withdrawal of the charge through oxygen atom by the metal ions. The molar conductance values for the complexes in formamide (10^{-3} M) are quite low ($2.7-5.0\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting their nonionic nature. The conductance values thus supplement the ir findings that SO₂Cl⁻ groups are covalently bonded to the metal ions. The bidentate mode of coordination of the chlorosulphate group is supported by the positions of the $\nu_{as}\text{ SO}_2$ bands (1250 ± 10 , $1180 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_s\text{ SO}_2$ bands ($1070-1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all the complexes.

The C=C and C=N stretching frequencies of the acridine molecule are observed at higher wave number ($1585-1595$ and $1620-1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively) in its complexes suggesting the coordination of the acridine to the metal chlorosulphates². Similarly, the ring vibrational bands are shifted to higher frequencies; at $1555-1570$ (8a), $630-670$ (6a) and $425-450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (16b) on coordination of pyridine and bipyridine to the metal ions³. The N-O stretching vibration (1243 cm^{-1}) in the uncoordinated pyridine-*N*-oxide is shifted to lower wavenumber ($1190-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes, indicating a decrease in the π -bond character of the N-O bond as a result of its coordination through oxygen atom. The participation of oxygen atom in coordination is further supported by the presence of M-O band at $370-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The other low frequency bands at $405-460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M-N stretching vibrations.

The magnetic moment values of the complexes are close to the theoretical values for the respective trivalent ions (Table I). The emission spectra of the europium complexes exhibit bands at $18500-18700$ and $21150-21500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to the transitions, ${}^7F_3 \leftarrow {}^5D_0$ and ${}^7F_1 \leftarrow {}^5D_0$, respectively.

The observed stoichiometry (1:2 for monodentate ligands and 1:1 for bidentate ligand) and the ir data indicate an octacoordination around the metal ions.

Experimental

The ligands (all B.D.H.) and the oxides of Eu, Tm and Yb (Aldrich) were used as such. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide and formamide (E. Merck) was distilled before use.

Lanthanum benzoates: The metal oxide of Eu, Tm or Yb was made into paste by adding water (5 ml). The paste was dissolved in 6 *M* HCl (6 ml)

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Yield %	Molar conductivity $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)					
				M	S	Cl	C	H	N
Eu(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Py	70	4.6	3.4	28.20 (28.25)	14.66 (14.71)	15.89 (15.81)	18.32 (18.38)	1.50 (1.54)	4.33 (4.29)
Eu(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Bipy	65	2.6	3.5	23.74 (23.32)	14.71 (14.76)	16.01 (15.36)	18.49 (18.43)	1.28 (1.24)	4.37 (4.30)
Eu(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ PyNO	63	3.1	3.4	22.61 (22.16)	14.10 (14.03)	14.98 (15.03)	17.11 (17.52)	1.49 (1.47)	4.11 (4.09)
Eu(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Ac	67	4.8	3.3	18.00 (17.80)	11.31 (11.20)	12.38 (12.10)	36.01 (36.57)	2.12 (2.12)	3.29 (3.28)
Tm(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Py	65	4.8	7.3	25.11 (25.19)	14.41 (14.34)	15.26 (15.41)	18.00 (17.91)	1.50 (1.50)	4.15 (4.18)
Tm(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Bipy	60	2.7	7.4	25.20 (25.27)	14.43 (14.39)	15.26 (15.46)	17.90 (17.86)	1.20 (1.21)	4.19 (4.19)
Tm(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ PyNO	60	3.9	7.3	24.13 (24.04)	13.74 (13.69)	14.72 (14.71)	17.03 (17.09)	1.40 (1.43)	4.01 (3.97)
Tm(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Ac	55	4.2	7.6	19.49 (19.40)	11.08 (11.04)	11.91 (11.86)	35.94 (35.86)	2.03 (2.08)	3.24 (3.22)
Yb(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Py	65	4.4	4.4	25.69 (25.65)	14.30 (14.25)	15.36 (15.32)	17.88 (17.80)	4.51 (4.49)	4.16 (4.15)
Yb(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Bipy	60	2.9	4.5	25.70 (25.72)	14.93 (14.30)	15.31 (15.36)	17.91 (17.85)	1.20 (1.20)	4.20 (4.16)
Yb(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ PyNO	65	4.2	4.4	24.51 (24.48)	13.57 (13.61)	14.66 (14.62)	17.04 (16.99)	1.44 (1.43)	3.98 (3.98)
Yb(SO ₄ Cl) ₂ Ac	60	5.2	4.3	19.68 (19.78)	11.05 (10.99)	11.80 (11.81)	35.74 (35.69)	2.03 (2.03)	3.23 (3.20)

and the solution was neutralised to incipient precipitation with 1 M NH₄OH adjusted to pH 2 with 1 M HCl. The solution was diluted to 200 ml, warmed to near boiling treated with sodium benzoate (1 M; 40 ml) over a period of 1 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was washed free from chloride ions and dried under reduced pressure. The benzoate was dehydrated at 85°.

Lanthanone chlorosulphates: The dehydrated benzoate of Eu, Tm or Yb (~ 5 g) was added in portions to excess of chlorosulphuric acid (~25 ml) kept in a closed reaction vessel and the temperature of the reaction mixture was not allowed to rise above 40°. The vigorous reaction was allowed to subside, and the solution was stirred for ~ 6 h. The resulting solid was washed with chlorosulphuric acid and thionyl chloride and dried under reduced pressure at 60-80°.

Preparation of complexes: A solution of the metal-chlorosulphate (0.05 mol) in boiling *N,N*-dimethylformamide (~ 30 ml) was mixed with excess of hot ligand solution (0.05 mol) in the same solvent and the mixture was shaken at 60°. The pyridine complexes separated out immediately. The other complexes were obtained in about a week. The solid complexes were washed with dimethyl formamide and dry ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Microanalyses were carried out with Thomas and Coleman analyser, Carlo Erba 1106. The complexes were analysed for metal contents by EDTA titration using bromopyrogallol red and eriochrome black T

as indicators⁴. The estimation of sulphur and chlorine were done gravimetrically⁵. The infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and diffuse reflectance spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer using MgO as calibrant. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a vibrating sample magnetometer model 155 at room temperature. The electrical conductivities of 1 mM solution in formamide were obtained using a Systronic 302 conductivity bridge at room temperature.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (S.R.A.Z., M.A.Z.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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